

ENGINE BRACKET STRUCTURAL AND FATIGUE ANALYSIS

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Abstract

The engine mounting plays an important role in reducing the noise, vibrations and harshness for improving vehicle ride comfort. The first and the foremost function of an engine mounting bracket is to properly balance the engine on aero plane wing for good motion control as well as good isolation.

This project deals structural and fatigue analysis of engine bracket operating at three different temperatures with applied loads. Normal operating loads are applied and thermal loads are kept at room temperatures, -40°C and +52°C conditions. Fatigue life is evaluated at critical locations. Goodman criteria is used for means stress correction and S-N curve is used to evaluate the number of cycles. Cumulative fatigue damage is carried out using Miner's rule. Critical locations are evaluated for fatigue life and damage estimation.

The results are evaluated and verification is done for strength and durability of the engine bracket operation at different temperature environments. Fasteners selection verification is carried out in the current analysis.

Keywords: Reducing the noise, Structural and fatigue analysis, Miner's rule

1. Introduction

When designing critical components for aircraft engines, today's designers are constantly challenged with the trade between performance requirements for strength and stiffness on one hand and size and weight on the other. Loading brackets on jet engines play a very critical role: they must support the weight of the engine during handling without breaking or warping. However, a jet travels across different regions of the world during flight. The changes in temperatures occur from -40°C to +52°C, which may contribute to the bracket failure due to the fatigue phenomenon occurring during the temperature change.

Structural strength analysis refers to the strength of the component to carry the load until failure. Failure is included here as plastic failure or fracture. However, in current study plastic failure is considered as potential failure of the bracket with respect to applied loads. Bracket stresses more than the yield strength are considered as failure of the bracket.

Fatigue analysis itself usually refers to one of two methodologies: either the Stress-Life (S-N) or S-N method, commonly referred to as Total Life since it makes no distinction between initiating or growing a crack, or the Local Strain or Strain-Life (e-N) method, commonly referred to as the Crack Initiation method which concerns itself only with the initiation of a crack.

Figure.1 : Engine Bracket CAD Model

Figure 2: Engine Bracket Mounting Positions

1.1 ENGINE BRACKET GEOMETRY/DIMENSIONAL DESCRIPTION

The engine bracket is made up of Ti-6Al-4V alloy, it is a high weight to strength ratio material. Basic geometry details are provided below:

Figure 3 : Fasteners and Lug Location Details

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

This project deals structural and fatigue analysis of engine bracket operating at three different temperatures with applied loads.

CASE I: Normal operating loads are applied and thermal loads are kept at room temperatures. Deformation and stress results are evaluated.

CASE II: Normal operating loads are applied and thermal loads applied at -40°C . Deformation and stress results are evaluated. Fatigue life is evaluated at critical locations.

CASE III: Normal operating loads are applied and thermal loads applied at -52°C . Deformation and stress results are evaluated. Fatigue life is evaluated at critical locations.

2.1 MATERIAL PROPERTY DETAILS

Titanium is one of the most popular alloys in the titanium industry and makes up almost half of the titanium used in the world. It has excellent strength, low modulus of elasticity, high corrosion resistance, good weld ability and it is heat treatable. The addition of aluminum and vanadium increases the hardness of the material in the alloy matrix, improving its physical and mechanical properties.

- High tensile strength—Ti-6Al-4V's strength nears that of stainless steel, requiring high cutting forces.
- Low thermal conductivity—Heat does not readily transfer into the chip but rather flows into the cutting tool, which makes the cutting edge very hot during the machining process.
- High modulus of elasticity—Titanium is very “springy.” For a given force, it will deflect more than steel, which results in a higher likelihood of vibration, chatter, and poor chip formation.
- Shear mechanism—Titanium requires a sharp cutting edge to cut the material and avoid tearing and smearing, which will quickly lead to tool failure
- Yield strength is 903MPa and ultimate strength is 1017MPa.

3. ANALYSIS APPROACH AND FLOWCHART

Structural analyses are performed at different operating temperatures and loading conditions. Horizontal, vertical and inclined loads are constant at all temperature conditions. Analyses flow chart is shown in below figures.

Structural Analysis @ Room Temperature

Horizontal, Vertical and Inclined loads are applied simultaneously

Structural Analysis @ -40°C Temperature

Horizontal, Vertical and Inclined loads are applied simultaneously

Structural Analysis @ +52°C Temperature

Horizontal, Vertical and Inclined loads are applied simultaneously

Fatigue Calculations

Fatigue strength and life calculations based on Goodman and S-N Curve

3.1 FE MODELING DETAILS OF ENGINE BRACKET

FE modeling of engine bracket is carried out with higher order hex and tetrahedral elements. Higher order elements are used to ensure the accuracy. Critical regions are captured with fine mesh. Averaged and un-averaged study is carried out to ensure the element density. Difference between averaged and un-averaged results are less than 5%.

SUMMARIZE SHAPE TESTING FOR ALL SELECTED ELEMENTS

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<<<<<<          SHAPE TESTING SUMMARY          >>>>>>
<<<<<<          FOR ALL SELECTED ELEMENTS        >>>>>>
-----
| Element count      208 SURF154 |
|                   796 SOLID186 |
|                   149410 SOLID187 |
|-----|
| Total             150414 |
|-----|
Test          Number tested  Warning count  Error count  Warn+Err %
-----
Aspect Ratio  150414          1             0             0.00 %
Parallel Deviation  796              0             0             0.00 %
Maximum Angle  150414            1             0             0.00 %
Jacobian Ratio  150206            0             0             0.00 %
Warping Factor   796                0             0             0.00 %
Any             150414            1             0             0.00 %
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Fig.5 Meshed model Engine bracket

3.2 LOADING CONDITION DETAILS – ROOM TEMPERATURE

Force of 35586N is applied at the lug location in vertical direction w.r.t local co-ordinate system as shown in below figure.

Figure 3.2 : Vertical Force Application

Engine bracket is evaluated for deformations and different stresses. von-Mises stress is considered for factor of safety estimation

Figure 6: Total Deformation Plot

3.3 STRESS RESULTS

Max von-Mises stress of 465MPa is observed at lug location and it is less than the material allowable yield strength of 903MPa with FOS of 1.9

Table. 1 : FOS Details

Max Stress, MPa	465.0
Yield Strength, MPa	903.0
FOS	1.9

Figure 7: Total Deformation Plot

3.4 FASTENER CALCULATIONS

Fastener's reaction forces are evaluated and tabulated. Fasteners with M10 size with grade of 10.9 is considered in the current calculations. Fastener nomenclature is shown in the figure below.

Figure 8 : Fastener Nomenclature

Figure 9 : Fastener Location Details

Fastener reaction forces are estimated w.r.t local co-ordinate system as shown in above figure. The X and Y directional forces are acting as shear load and hence resultant is taken for shear stress evaluation. Y directional forces are action as normal forces taken to estimate the normal stress.

Table-1 : Fastener Reaction Force Details

Bolt	Reaction Force, N		
	X	Y	Z
Bolt-1	15180	13594	-8635.2
Bolt-2	2240.7	19819	-26104
Bolt-3	-1748.7	16953	-22286
Bolt-4	-15672	16624	-9061.3

- Normal Stress = $\sigma_n = \frac{\text{Axial Force}}{\text{Area}}$
- Shear Stress = $\tau = \frac{\text{Shear Force}}{\text{Area}}$
- Equivalent Stress = $\sigma = \sqrt{(\sigma_n)^2 + 3\tau^2}$

Table-2 : Bolt Specification

Bolt Specification	M10 – Grade10.9
Shank Diameter, mm	10
Area, mm ²	78.5
Allowable Strength, MPa	900.0

Table-3 : Fastener Result Summary

Axial Force, N (Y-Direction)	Resultant Shear Load, N (X & Z- Direction Resultant)	Axial Stress, MPa	Shear Stress, MPa	Equivalent Stress, MPa	Allowable Strength, MPa	FOS
13594	17464.2	173.1	222.4	422.2	900	2.1
19819	26200.0	252.3	333.6	630.5	900	1.4
16953	22354.5	215.9	284.6	538.2	900	1.7
16624	18103.0	211.7	230.5	451.9	900	2.0

All fasteners meet the intended design requirement of FOS 1.

4. Conclusion

Based on the Simulation results on engine bracket, it can be concluded that, Engine bracket is safe for operating in different regions of world with different temperature variations. Fasteners selected for the engine bracket assembly are safe enough to take the loads at all different temperatures. This analysis method reduces the time of calculation and different experiments can be carried out. Engine bracket optimization can be carried out to reduce the weight by using advance optimization algorithms. Different materials can be used which are having high strength and less cost.

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A Brief Author Biography

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2nd Anand Mattikali– Associate professor and HOD of Mechanical Engineering Maratha Mandal Engineering College, Belagavi, Karantaka. Having 20+ years of experience in teaching and Research in Composite material.